

Experimental assessment of photonic down-conversion techniques for analog new-radio upstream

Miquel Masanas, María C. Santos, Josep Prat

Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Teoria del senyal i comunicacions, Barcelona, Spain

e-mail: miquel.masanas@upc.edu

ABSTRACT

This paper explores the feasibility of Intermediate Frequency (IF) detection from a directly modulated Radio Frequency (RF) optical signal. We propose a method involving optical series re-modulation of an RF over Fiber (RFoF) signal and a down-converting frequency, resulting in unmodulated and modulated optical carrier repetitions separated by the target intermediate frequency. Two approaches are examined: employing a null point biased Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM) for electrical frequency doubling and utilizing intensity modulation for power efficiency.

Keywords: Radio-over-Fiber, Fronthaul Networks, Analog RoF, Photonic Mixing, Intermediate Frequency

1. INTRODUCTION

With the rising frequencies in new-radio wireless communication, Remote Radio Heads (RRH) are forecasted to be increasingly ubiquitous and capacity demanding, and fibre links, especially in point-to-multipoint structures, are efficient candidates to deliver the increased performance in a cost-effective manner. Therefore, there's a pressing need for seamless, low-cost signal conversion from the optical to the electrical domain and back. Integrating InP and SiPh electronics marks a significant advancement, enabling the transfer of complexity to the optical realm while achieving broader bandwidth and ideally linear responses, and allowing to include hardware outside the optical line terminal (OLT) that was before unpractical due to cost and footprint, such as external modulators, amplifiers, polarization optics, et. al. While efforts have been made to develop flexible and straightforward mobile optical fronthaul, particularly for the downstream (DS) direction, challenges persist in addressing the upstream (US) segment. Specifically, in flexible radio analog fronthaul technology, there's a push to avoid using electrical mixers in favour of photonic mixers. This approach promises enhanced dynamic range and spur rejection. Several strategies have been explored based on Semiconductor Optical Amplifier (SOA), four-wave mixing, dual parallel Mach-Zehnder modulators, optical hybrids and electro-absorption modulators [1]. Notably, optical frequency multiplication leveraging several configurations of the Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM) has shown promise, achieving multiplications from 2 to 12 [2, 3].

This paper explores the feasibility of achieving an Intermediate Frequency (IF) over fibre (IFoF) signal from a Radio Frequency (RF) over fibre (RFoF) signal, offering advantages such as higher responsivity, lower-speed transimpedance amplifiers (TIA) and analog to digital converters (DACs), and addressing chromatic dispersion amplitude fading at the OLT. Figure 1 shows the proposed approach for the US transmission, keeping the DS generic. The electrical section in the RRH is kept simple, just consisting in the bidirectional antenna, signal amplification and electro-optical (E/O) conversion both ways. Therefore, in the US after E/O the RF signal is modulated directly in the optical domain. A second optical modulation of a tone at a conversion frequency (f_{conv}) is performed to condition the signal for IF detection. The objective is to transition optically from the RF modulation to an optical spectrum that facilitates the detection at an intermediate frequency at the OLT photodetector. This process yields unmodulated and modulated optical carrier repetitions separated by the target intermediate frequency (f_{IF}). Two approaches are reported: the first involves employing the null point biased Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM), offering the advantage of the well-known electrical frequency doubling at the expense of increased insertion and operational loss. The second consists in a more power-efficient implementation and employs an electro-absorption modulator (EAM) to avoid the insertion and operational losses associated with MZMs, and notably, their polarization dependence.

Figure 1. Optical RF to IF down-conversion for US fronthaul in a cascaded configuration, low speed receiver.

Figure 2. Frequency down-conversion steps for a) NP amplitude modulation and b) QP intensity modulation.

In this paper, our focus is on a laboratory-level demonstration of IF detection of the RF signal. Both approaches are tested using a MZM modulator, either at null-point (NP) or quadrature point (QP), the latter emulating the behaviour of an EAM. The RF modulation is achieved using a 18 GHz BW directly modulated laser (DML), based on a distributed feedback (DFB) cavity. Specifically, we investigate RF modulation of 500 Mbaud QPSK at 10 and 15 GHz, and 16-QAM signals at 10 GHz with a down-converted frequency of 4 GHz.

2. PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION

The principle of operation of the system is shown in Figure 2 for both the frequency doubling NP amplitude modulation (AM), shown in a), and the power-efficient QP intensity modulation (IM), shown in b). Both start from the same RF modulation in the optical domain, and aim to achieve a spectral separation between optical unmodulated tones equal to $f_{RF} \pm f_{IF}$, which will place the distance between the resulting tones and data exactly at f_{IF} . Note that in the example in figure 2 the focus is on the $f_{RF} - f_{IF}$, which is more attractive from a practical viewpoint as it requires a lower local oscillator (LO) frequency. For the NP case, the required electrical tone is half this magnitude, thus $f_{conv} = (f_{RF} \pm f_{IF})/2$, as we rely on the separation between the upper and lower sidebands, shown in red and blue, respectively, and suppressing the original optical carrier. At the photodetector the beating between the lower sideband un-modulated tone (in blue) and the upper sideband modulated data (in red) will fall at exactly f_{IF} , and similarly for the upper sideband unmodulated tone and the lower data sideband. On the other hand, for the QP case with $f_{conv} = f_{RF} \pm f_{IF}$, the beatings between the sideband unmodulated tones, in red and blue, and the original modulated sidebands, in green, are detected along with the beatings between the original unmodulated wavelength in green and the modulated sidebands in blue and red at f_{IF} distance.

Considering a data low-pass equivalent of bandwidth BW_E , the total spectral width with the NP strategy, is $3f_{RF} + 2BW_E - f_{IF}$, where BW_E is the total data bandwidth, but the useful spectral width is, $f_{RF} + 2BW_E$. For the QP case, the total spectral width is $4f_{RF} + 2BW_E - 2f_{IF}$, with a useful spectral width $2(f_{RF} + BW_E)$, being less spectrally efficient than the NP strategy.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The experimental set-up is presented in Figure 3 a). We assess the Bit Error Rate (BER) performance against the received optical power (ROP) for a 500 MHz data signal, with $f_{RF} = 10$ GHz and both QPSK (1 Gbps) and 16QAM (2Gbps), and also for 15 GHz and QPSK. In all cases the downconverted frequency is $f_{IF} = 4$ GHz. The transmitted signal undergoes square root raised cosine (SRRC) filtering both at the transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx), employing a roll-off factor of 1. Figure 3 b) shows the constellation performances in error-free conditions. At 15 GHz, inter-symbol interference due to the laser frequency response and nonlinearities is observed.

Figure 3. a) Schematic of the experimental set-up. b) Error-free constellation diagrams of the studied scenarios.

The experimental setup is as follows: The RFoF modulator is comprised by a DML operated at a bias current of 60 mA with a 3 dB bandwidth (BW) of 18.5 GHz, and driven by a 30 GHz electrical amplifier to achieve a modulation index (m_{IM}) of 0.6 for the QPSK modulation and 0.5 for the 16QAM. The output state of polarization (SOP) is controlled at the input of the Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM), with 9 dB of insertion and operational losses at 9 GHz 3 dB BW, operating at the NP and driven with a 9 V_{pp} sinusoidal signal. The 10 and 15 GHz RF NP cases use 3 and 5.5 GHz of f_{conv} , respectively, while the QP cases use 6 and 11 GHz. Then, back-to-back (btb) and 25 km of standard single-mode fibre (SSMF) are used to assess system performance. Finally, photodetection is done with an 8 GHz PIN+TIA photodetector and processed with a 12.5 GHz real-time oscilloscope (RTO) to provide sensitivity performance.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Null point strategy

Figure 4. Results of the null point approach. Left: BER against ROP. Right: spectral occupation.

The BER performance and spectral results for the NP strategy are shown in Figure 4. The optical spectra show a residue of the optical carrier due to the finite extinction ratio (ER) of the MZM. After detection, this residue gives a pure tone beating at the applied tone frequency shown in the electrical spectrum at 3 and 5.5 GHz for the 10 and 15 GHz RF cases, respectively. The electrical spectra also show the tone beating between the upper and lower un-modulated sidebands beating at 6 and 11 GHz, respectively. Most importantly, both electrical spectra show the down-conversion at $f_{IF} = 4$ GHz resulting from the beating between the un-modulated tones and the modulated RF carriers. In the 10 GHz RF case, the RTO bandwidth allows to detect the beating between the un-modulated and modulated carriers separated at the original RF frequency.

The BER performance against ROP shows in blue the btb scenario and in red the 25 km of SSMF, while continuous and discontinuous lines represent 15 and 10 GHz of RF carrier, respectively. Diamond and circular markers represent QPSK and 16 QAM each. Sensitivity for FEC threshold is considered at 10^{-3} . The 10 GHz QPSK cases are at -19 dBm and -19.5 dBm for the btb and 25 km tests, respectively, while 15 GHz QPSK falls at -20 and -19.5 dBm for the btb and 25 km cases, all in all leading to very close performances. The 16 QAM results for both btb and 25 km yield very close performances, at -14 dBm, with 5 to 6 dB power budget penalty with respect to QPSK.

4.2 Intensity modulation strategy

Figure 5 shows the BER performance and spectral results for the QP strategy. The electrical spectrum shows the central wavelength and unmodulated sidebands beating at 6 and 11 GHz for the 10 and 15 GHz RF down-conversion, respectively. The down-conversion resulting from the beating between the un-modulated tones and the modulated RF carriers can be seen at $f_{IF} = 4$ GHz like in the NP case. In the optical domain the now dominant central wavelength λ_0 is apparent, with the un-modulated MZM generated sidebands at 6 and 11 GHz, respectively.

Figure 5. Results of the quadrature point approach. Right: BER against ROP. Left: spectral occupation.

Separated f_{RF} from both the central λ_0 and the un-modulated sidebands, the data lobes can be distinguished, and finally the interleaving between the upper and lower un-modulated sidebands and the λ_0 modulated sideband present similar power levels. The modulated sidebands close to λ_0 , albeit at much lower power, can be still observed.

The sensitivity levels for both 10 and 15 GHz QPSK cases are at -19 dBm and -20.5 dBm for the btb and 25 km cases, respectively. The 16 QAM cases for both btb and 25 km have very close performances at -15.5 dBm, with power budget penalties with respect to the QPSK cases between 3.5 and 5 dB. Very notably, we measured the transmitter optical output power and observed a 3 dB gain of the QP relative to the NP approach.

4.3 System comparison

Key observations from the presented results are an increased power budget from the QP strategy and a more efficient spectrum and bandwidth use from the NP strategy. On the one side, the QP has yielded increased 3 dB power output with the same modulation conditions by only shifting the modulator bias, even considering a higher f_{conv} which could be affected by extra loss given the BW limitation in the MZM. Further improvement when using flat frequency response, shorter EAMs is expected. On the Rx side, the QP provided between 1 and 2 dB increased sensitivity. A small sensitivity improvement is seen between the 25 km fibre case and the btb, which could be caused by dispersion interaction of the DML and the optical fibre and will be studied further in the future. On the other hand, the NP strategy achieved similar performances from the Rx perspective with half the f_{conv} and modulator BW requirements and with increased spectral efficiency, even more so considering the useful spectral span.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we investigated optical frequency down-conversion for the US link A-RoF based mobile fronthaul. Two strategies are evaluated: a MZM in null-point, showing efficient use of the electrical and optical bandwidth, and intensity modulation, shown with a MZM in quadrature point but compatible with industry-mature EAMs, with increased power budget and reduced footprint. We have demonstrated sensitivities of -19 to -21 dBm for a QPSK modulation at 1 Gbps, and -14 to -16 dBm for 16 QAM at 2 Gbps in both setups, non-dependent with the original RF studied frequencies of 10 and 15 GHz, showing good scalability of the down-conversion technique. These results show good performance of optical alternatives to electrical mixing for IFoF links.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has received funding from grant CONFLOC (PID2022-137754OB) funded by MCIN / AEI / 10.13039 / 501100011033 / FEDER, UE and EU's Horizon Europe Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101073265 (EWOC).

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Tang *et al.* Photonics-Based Microwave Frequency Mixing: Methodology and Applications. *Laser & Photonics Reviews* 2019, 14, 1800350
- [2] Guohua Qi *et al.* "Generation and distribution of a wide-band continuously tunable millimeter-wave signal with an optical external modulation technique," in *IEEE Trans. on MW. Th. and Tech.*, vol. 53, no. 10, pp. 3090-3097, Oct. 2005
- [3] Zihang Zhu *et al.* "Filterless frequency 12-tupling optical millimeter-wave generation using two cascaded dual-parallel Mach-Zehnder modulators," *Appl. Opt.* 54, 9432-9440 (2015)